

The spatial patterns of living connected: from the Web to social media and sharing economy platforms

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STRUCTURED ABSTRACT

Aim of the contribution

This work aims to present the impacts of digital connection on the forms of interaction between contemporary society and urban space. To this end, we analyze the new patterns of information circulation, especially from the development of the internet, social media, and sharing economy platforms, and the encouragement of new forms of use, circulation, and production of urban space.

Value of the contribution

This work contributes to the understanding of information circulation and digital connection as a cultural, economic, and spatial phenomenon that varies from one place to another and has global impacts due to the speed of information circulation. From this, it is possible to perceive the changes in this process over time, focusing on the period from 1990 to the present day. Based on this information, this work presents the spatial patterns of living connected.

Research outline

This work is part of a theoretical-conceptual analysis that integrates a doctoral research focused on the relationship between digital platforms and urban space. In general, with the development of the internet, the relationship between humans and urban space has been transformed, largely due to new forms of organization, circulation, and access to information.

The guiding question of this research is: "How has the internet impacted our relationship with urban space?" This question is answered through the construction of a historical analysis that demonstrates different moments in the relationship between the internet, society, and urban space. This analysis has historical milestones such as the

diffusion of the World Wide Web in the 1990s, the development of social networks from the 2000s, and the growth of digital sharing economy platforms in the 2010s.

To construct this analysis, bibliographic references are used that present narratives about the history of the computer (Marshall, 2015), the internet (Ryan, 2010; McCullough, 2018), and digital media (Manovich, 2001). Additionally, bibliographic references on the history of social networks (Vilicic, 2015) and sharing economy platforms (Gallagher, 2018) are also used.

As a result, it is understood that the internet has transformed our relationship with space in various ways. Initially, this relationship was more controlled, as the connection was sporadic: it was possible to choose to be connected or not. Even so, the connection stimulated new forms of long-distance social interaction, expanding spaces of sociability — which were previously concentrated on the local scale, in family and neighborhood interactions — besides creating new spatial typologies, such as internet cafés.

The internet has also transformed how we understand and locate ourselves in urban space (through the use of tools like Google Maps and Waze), how we move, and how we transport goods (with Uber, Ifood, etc.). Social networks nowadays allow us to access the daily lives of distant places and people who increasingly become part of our daily reality, through, for example, Instagram. These new networks of people and places, in turn, stimulate new consumer desires, which are exploited by sharing economy platforms.

Finally, the presented overview demonstrates how the process of internet diffusion has gone through different phases, showing moments of optimism regarding the possibility of free and democratic access to information. Currently, it can be said that researchers from various fields are increasingly adopting a more critical stance towards this process and the social inequalities associated with it.

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